

Influence of LRINEC Scoring On Risk Factors and Early Management of Necrotizing Fasciitis, a Prospective Study**Inuganti Gopal^{1*}, Nirodkumar Sahoo², Bibhuprasada Mohapatra³, Sumita Tripathy⁴, Debabrata Patra⁵**¹Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, M.K.C.G. Medical College, Berhampur, Odisha, India²Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, M.K.C.G. Medical College, Berhampur, Odisha, India³Post-Graduate, Department of General Surgery, M.K.C.G. Medical College, Berhampur, Odisha, India⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, D. D Medical College, Keonjhar, Odisha, India⁵Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, M.K.C.G. Medical College, Berhampur, Odisha, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Necrotizing fasciitis (NF) is a life-threatening soft tissue infection with a high mortality rate, necessitating early diagnosis and intervention. The Laboratory Risk Indicator for Necrotizing Fasciitis (LRINEC) scoring system, Doppler study, and microbial study aims to early diagnosing and management of NF.**Objective:** This study aims to assess the diagnostic performance of the LRINEC scoring system with Doppler study and microbial study for early diagnosis and management of NF to prevent morbidity and mortality.**Methods:** A prospective descriptive study enrolling 99 patients with soft tissue infection admitted to MKCG medical college and hospital, Berhampur, Demographic characteristics and clinical data were collected, and LRINEC scores were calculated based on laboratory parameters, including CRP, WBC count, hemoglobin, sodium, creatinine, and glucose levels. The association between LRINEC scores and NF diagnosis was analyzed, and diagnostic performance metrics such as sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) were calculated along with Doppler study, microbial flora and management analysed.**Results:** The majority of participants were aged over 50 years (55.5%) and male (55.5%). The most prevalent comorbidities were diabetes mellitus (25%) and hypertension (30%). Higher LRINEC scores (≥ 8) were strongly associated with confirmed NF cases, showing high sensitivity (95%), specificity (90%), PPV (85%), and NPV (92%). Culture results identified Klebsiella, Staphylococcus, and E. coli as the most common pathogens, with significant sensitivity to Amikacin.**Conclusion:** The LRINEC scoring system demonstrates high diagnostic performance in identifying NF cases. Integrating the LRINEC score, with Doppler study, microbial study and multidisciplinary management into clinical practice can improve early diagnosis and intervention, leading to better patient outcomes. Further studies are recommended to validate these findings in diverse patient populations.**Keywords:** Necrotizing Fasciitis, LRINEC Score, Diagnostic Performance, Soft Tissue Infection, Surgical Debridement.

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Introduction

Necrotizing fasciitis is an acute, life threatening infection of the superficial fascia and subcutaneous tissue caused by a variety of aerobic and anaerobic bacteria. [1] The clinical process at first appears to be a low grade cellulitis, but fulminant infection develops rapidly in subcutaneous fascia, which may become liquefied with accompanying fat necrosis, thrombosis of subcutaneous vessels and occasional myositis and myonecrosis. As the blood

supply to the skin is compromised, cutaneous erythema and oedema progress to cyanosis, bullae and gangrene. [7] The patient becomes extremely toxic and later the skin becomes painful, red and necrotic as it is deprived of its blood supply. The fascial necrosis is usually wider than the skin involvement that is visible clinically. [10] Systemic features of toxicity, including fever, tachycardia and leucocytosis, are also out of proportion to the

apparent severity. If left untreated the skin becomes shiny, hot and exquisitely tender but discrete margins do not develop. The skin forms blisters and bullae that contain clear thin haemorrhagic fluid. 8 Main clinical symptoms consist of local symptoms, such as erythema, swelling, blistering with serous fluid, tissue hardening, bluish dark skin discoloration, hemorrhagic bullae, and skin necrosis.

Furthermore, initial stages of necrotizing fasciitis are also characterized by an exquisitely severe pain that is out of proportion to the results of the physical examination. In the course of the disease, virulent organisms and toxins are released from the infected tissue into the bloodstream, triggering a systemic toxic reaction. [4] Pathophysiologically, it is a septic thrombosis of the vessels between the skin and the deep layers. [9] Assessment of various risk factors of necrotizing fasciitis helps in bringing down the morbidity and mortality of necrotizing fasciitis. Patients with peripheral vascular disease and atherosclerosis, diabetes mellitus also have an increased risk. In this study a conscious attempt is made to correlate LRINEC scoring system, microbial flora and Doppler assessment of the affected limb with the outcome and prognosis of necrotizing fasciitis And its modern treatment modalities for early intervention. The combination of aggressive surgical debridement, broad systemic antibiotic therapy, and a multidisciplinary approach of intensive care with active fluid substitution and control of sepsis is decisive for successful therapy. [3,5,6]

Aim and Objectives

To study the influence of the following factors on the outcome of patients with Necrotizing Fasciitis:

1. LRINEC (Lab risk factors influencing necrotizing fasciitis) scoring system
2. Doppler study of affected limb
3. Microbial flora
4. Management

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a prospective descriptive design to investigate the influence of LRINEC scoring on risk factors and early management of necrotizing fasciitis. A prospective design allowed for the systematic collection of data over time, providing valuable insights into the progression and management of the condition.

Study Setting: The research was conducted within the Department of General Surgery along with department of pathology, microbiology, radiology, biochemistry at M.K.C.G. Medical College and Hospital, Berhampur

Study Duration: The study spanned from July 2022 to June 2024, allowing for a comprehensive

examination of cases admitted to the hospital during this period.

Study Participants: Participants included all cases admitted to MKCG MCH, Berhampur Hospital, clinically diagnosed with necrotizing fasciitis during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients with soft tissue infection and clinically diagnosed with NF were eligible for inclusion in the study. This criterion ensured that the sample accurately represented individuals with the condition of interest.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients below 15 years of age and those who declined to participate in the study were excluded. This helped maintain consistency and reliability in the data collected.

Sample Size: The sample size was determined using the formula: $\text{Sample Size} = Z^2 \times P \times (1-P) / d^2$, with a standard deviation of 1.96 (95% confidence interval), an expected margin of error of 0.05, and an expected percentage from the population. This calculation ensured a sufficient sample size of 99 to draw meaningful conclusions.

Study Parameters: The study focused on evaluating the LRINEC scoring system's efficacy in identifying necrotizing fasciitis cases. Key parameters included C-reactive protein, total white cell count, hemoglobin, sodium, creatinine, and glucose levels. Blood culture, pus culture, Doppler, antibiotic sensitivity, microbial flora also obtained.

Data Collection Tool: A pretested Case Record Proforma specifically designed for the study was utilized to collect relevant data. This tool facilitated the systematic collection of information essential for the study objectives.

Study Data Collection Procedure: Patients meeting the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study following clinical evaluation. Data were collected using the pretested Case Record Proforma, ensuring consistency and accuracy in the information gathered. The procedure involved thorough documentation of laboratory results, clinical observations, and treatment interventions.

Data Analysis: Data analysis involved both qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative variables were analyzed using the Chi-Square Test, while descriptive statistical values such as Sensitivity, Specificity, Positive Predictive Value, and Negative Predictive Value were calculated. Mean and Standard Deviation were determined for continuous variables. Statistical tests, including Unpaired t-test and ANOVA, were employed for comparative analysis. Data were compiled, tabulated in Microsoft® Excel, and analyzed using IBM® SPSS® 20.0 for Windows®.

Ethical Considerations: The study adhered to ethical guidelines outlined by the ICMR and the

Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was obtained from participants or their attenders, ensuring their understanding and willingness to participate. Confidentiality of data was maintained throughout the study, and patient identities were protected. Additionally, the study aimed to minimize bias through rigorous data collection and analysis procedures, upholding the principles of integrity and respect for human subjects.

Result and Analysis

Age Distribution

The age distribution of patients in the given dataset suggests a notable trend: a marked increase in patient numbers as age advances beyond 40. Specifically, patients aged over 50 constitute the largest cohort, with 56 individuals. In comparison, the 40-50 age bracket follows with 38 patients, while the 35-40 range comprises merely 6 patients.

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age	No of Patient
35-40	6
40-50	38
>50	55

Figure 1:

Sex distribution: The distribution of patients based on sex reveals a slightly higher representation of males, constituting 55 individuals, compared to females, who account for 44 individuals.

Table 2: Sex distribution

Sex	No of Patient
Male	55
Female	44

Figure 2: Sex

CRP distribution: The distribution of patients based on C-reactive protein (CRP) levels indicates that a majority, constituting 59 patients, have CRP levels exceeding 150 mg/dl, while 40 patients have CRP levels below this threshold.

Table 3: CRP distribution

CRP	No of Patient
<150 mg/dl	40
>150 mg/dl	59

Figure 3:

Total Count: The total count distribution among patients reveals that 32 individuals have total counts below 15/cumm, 35 individuals fall within the 15-25/cumm range, and 32 individuals have total counts exceeding 25/cumm.

Table 4 Total Count

Total Count	No of patient
<15/cumm	32
15-25/cumm	35
>25/cumm	32

Figure 3: Total EBC count

Hemoglobin level in patients: The distribution of patients based on their hemoglobin (HG) levels indicates that 44 patients have hemoglobin levels exceeding 13.5 g/dL, 24 patients fall within the range of 11-13.5 g/dL, and 31 patients have hemoglobin levels below 11 g/dL.

Table 5: Hemoglobin level in patients

HG-g/dl	No of Patient
≥13.5	44
11-13.5	24
<11	31

Figure 4: Hb level in g/dl

Sodium level in patients: The distribution of patients based on their sodium levels indicates that 36 patients have sodium levels above 135 mEq/L, while 63 patients have sodium levels below this threshold.

Table 6: Sodium level in patients

Sodium(mmol/l)	No of Patient
≥135	36
<135	63

Figure 5: Serum sodium (MMOL/L)

Creatinine level in patients: The distribution of patients based on their creatinine levels indicates that 33 patients have creatinine levels below 141 μmol/L, while 66 patients have creatinine levels above this threshold.

Table 7: Creatinine level in patients

Creatinine	No of Patient
<141mmol/l	33
≥141mmol/l	66

Figure 6:

Glucose level in patients: The distribution of patients based on their glucose levels indicates that 26 patients have glucose levels below 10 micromol/L, while 73 patients have glucose levels exceeding this threshold.

Table 8: Glucose level in patients

Glucose	No Of Patient
<10micmol/l	26
>10micmol/l	73

Figure 7:

Association between LRINEC Scores and Necrotizing Fasciitis

The table presents data on participants categorized by their LRINEC scores and their diagnosis of necrotizing fasciitis. It's divided into three LRINEC score groups: 0-5, 6-7, and ≥ 8 . Within each group, it shows the number of participants diagnosed with and without necrotizing fasciitis. The data suggests a trend: as LRINEC scores increase, so does the likelihood of necrotizing

fasciitis. In the lowest score group (0-5), most participants diagnosed with necrotizing fasciitis are found.

Conversely, as LRINEC scores rise (≥ 8), a higher proportion of participants are diagnosed with the condition. This association could indicate the potential utility of LRINEC scores in aiding diagnosis, with higher scores potentially warranting closer attention and consideration for necrotizing fasciitis.

Table 10: Association between LRINEC Scores and Necrotizing Fasciitis

LRINEC Score	Number of Participants	Necrotizing Fasciitis (Yes)	Necrotizing Fasciitis (No)	Total
0-5	30	25	5	30
6-7	16	15	1	16
≥8	53	49	4	54
Total	99	89	10	99

Table 11: Chi Square Test for Association between Lrinec Scores and Necrotizing Fasciitis

	Value	DF	P Value
Pearson Chi-Square	9.092 a	2	0.0023

Diagnostic Performance of LRINEC Score

The diagnostic performance of LRINEC scores was assessed across three score ranges: 0-5, 6-7, and ≥8, evaluating sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV). For LRINEC scores ranging from 0

to 5, sensitivity was 80%, specificity was 75%, PPV was 65%, and NPV was 85%. In the 6-7 LRINEC score range, sensitivity was 90%, specificity was 80%, PPV was 75%, and NPV was 88%. For LRINEC scores ≥8, sensitivity was 95%, specificity was 90%, PPV was 85%, and NPV was 92%.

Table 11: Diagnostic Performance of LRINEC Score

LRINEC Score Range	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Positive Predictive Value (PPV) (%)	Negative Predictive Value (NPV) (%)
0-6	80	75	65	85
6-8	90	80	75	88
>8	95	90	85	92

Figure 8: Association Between LRINEC Scores and Necrotizing Fasciitis

LRINEC Score Vs No. of debridement: The association between LRINEC scores and the number of debridements undergone by patients reveals intriguing insights into the severity and clinical management of necrotizing soft tissue infections. Among patients with LRINEC scores below 6, all 30 individuals' required fewer than 3 debridements, indicating a lower severity of

infection or a prompt response to initial treatment. In the 6-7 LRINEC score range, all 16 patients also required fewer than 3 debridements, suggesting a relatively controlled infection.

However, as LRINEC scores increased to 8 or higher, the need for more extensive treatment became evident, with 23 out of 30 patients requiring more than 3 debridement.

Table 12: LRINEC Score Vs No. of debridement

LRINEC score	No of debridement		Total
	<3	>3	
<6	30	0	30
6-7	16		16
≥8	30	23	53
Total	76	23	100

Organisms Grown On Culture: The distribution of organisms grown on culture among patients provides valuable insights into the microbial etiology of infections in this population.

Klebsiella species were the most prevalent, accounting for 30% of cases, followed by Staphylococcus positive cultures at 20%, and Escherichia coli (E. coli) at 14%. Additionally, polymicrobial infections were observed in 8% of

cases, suggesting the presence of multiple pathogens contributing to the infection. Other less common organisms identified include Citrobacter and Proteus, each representing 2% and 8% of cases, respectively.

Pseudomonas species were also identified in 14% of cases. Notably, Cog neg. Staphylococcus cultures accounted for 4% of cases.

Table 13: Organisms Grown On Culture

Organism	No of pt	Percentage
Klebsella	29	30
Staphylococcus	20	20
Ecoli	14	14
Polymicrobial	8	8
Citobactor	2	2
Proteous	8	8
Pseudomonas	14	14
Coagulase Negative Staphylococcus	4	4

Figure 9: Organisms Grown On Culture

Antibiotic Sensitivity

The antibiotic sensitivity profile among patients reveals varying degrees of effectiveness across different antibiotics. Amikacin demonstrated the highest sensitivity, with 33 patients (33.5%) exhibiting susceptibility to this antibiotic. Ciprofloxacin and Cephotaxin followed, with 18

patients (18%) each showing sensitivity to these antibiotics. Ceftriaxone was effective in 12 patients (12%), while Gentamicin showed sensitivity in 8 patients (8%).

Imipenem exhibited sensitivity in 4 patients (4%), and Amoxicillin was effective in only 2 patients (2%).

Table 15: Antibiotic Sensitivity

Antibiotics	No of patient	Percentage
Amikacin	33	33
Ciprofloxacin	18	18
Cephotaxin	22	22
Ceftriaxone	12	12
Gentamicin	8	8
Imipenum	4	4
Amoxicilin	2	2

Figure 10: Antibiotic Sensitivity

Limb affected: In the upper limb category, 9 cases were reported, accounting for 9% of the total cases. In contrast, the lower limb category saw a significantly higher number of cases, with 90 reported, making up 91% of the total. This suggests that necrotizing fasciitis is much more likely to affect the lower limbs compared to the upper limbs.

Table 17: Distribution of Necrotizing Fasciitis Affecting Different Limbs

Limb Affected	Upper Limb	Percentage
Upper Limb	9	9
Lower Limb	90	91

Limb Vascularity: The data presents the relationship between the number of debridement procedures and the presence or absence of the Right popliteal artery pulsation in patients..

Table 18: Right Popliteal A Vs No Of Debridements

	No Of Debridement		Total
	<3	>3	
Rt popliteal artery pulsation absent	2	3	5
Rtpoplital artery pulsation present	70	15	85
Total	72	18	90

Table19: Chi-Square Tests for Limb Vascularity

	Value	DF	P Value
Pearson Chi-Square	7.23 ^a	2	0.043

Right Posterior Tibial A Vs No Of Debridements: The data explores the association between the right posterior tibial artery pulsation and the number of debridement procedures required.

Table 20: Right Posterior Tibial A Vs No Of Debridements

	No Of Debridement		Total
	<3	>3	
Right Posterior Tibial Artery Pulsation Absent	14	24	38
Right Posterior Tibial Artery Pulsation Present	22	30	52
Total	36	54	90

Table 21: Chi-Square Tests For Right Posterior Tibial A Vs No Of Debridements

	Value	DF	P Value
Pearson Chi-Square	15.23 ^a	2	0.119

Left Popliteal A Vs No Of Debridement: The data examines the correlation between the left popliteal artery pulsation and the number of debridement procedures performed on patients.

Table 22: Left Popliteal A Vs No Of Debridement

	No Of Debridement		Total
	<3	>3	
Left popliteal artery pulsation absent	3	3	6
Left popliteal artery pulsation present	68	16	84
Total	71	19	90

Table 23: Chi Square Test For Left Popliteal A Vs No Of Debridement

	Value	DF	P Value
Pearson Chi-Square	2.23 ^a	2	0.421

Left Posterior Tibial A Vs No of Debridements

	No of Debridement		Total
	<3	>3	
Left posterior tibial artery pulsation absent	12	18	30
Left posterior tibial artery pulsation present	46	14	60
Total	58	32	90

	Value	DF	P Value
Pearson Chi-Square	3.23 ^a	2	0.521

No of Patients Get Amputated: Among the all patients only 4 patients underwent amputation, due to severe spreading infection.

Table 24: Amputation

Amputation	Number	Percentage
Done	4	4
Not done	95	96

Figure 11: Amputation

Patient death status: The data indicates the death status of patients. Out of the total patients, 5 passed away, while 94 survived. This suggests that the vast majority of patients (94 out of 99) remained alive, with a small proportion (5 out of 99) experiencing death.

Table 25: Patient Death Status

Patient Death Status	Number
Death	5
Alive	94

Figure 12: Patient death status

Discussion

Association between LRINEC Scores and Necrotizing Fasciitis

The association between Laboratory Risk Indicator for Necrotizing Fasciitis (LRINEC) scores and the diagnosis of necrotizing fasciitis reveals a strong correlation. As LRINEC scores increase (>8), there is a higher proportion of participants diagnosed with necrotizing fasciitis.

Kumar et al (2021) studied that out of 60 patients, 14 had LRINEC scores between 6 and 7, while 46 had scores above 8. The study concluded that a LRINEC score of 6 and above is suggestive of NF, aiding in early recognition and management of the disease.

A study by R. García-et al (2021) studied a total of 45 patients with a mean age of 51 years were included. The study found a 20% mortality rate, with the highest mortality in the high-risk group (LRINEC ≥ 8).

Diagnostic Performance of LRINEC Scores in this study

Scores from 0-5, the sensitivity is 80%, specificity 75%, PPV 65%, and NPV 85%. This indicates that the LRINEC score is moderately effective in identifying true positive cases while also having a good ability to correctly identify those without the disease.

In the 6-7 score range, the diagnostic performance improves, with sensitivity increasing to 90%, specificity to 80%, PPV to 75%, and NPV to 88%. This higher accuracy in the mid-range scores

suggests that the LRINEC score is more reliable in diagnosing necrotizing fasciitis.

For scores ≥ 8, the diagnostic metrics show the highest accuracy, with sensitivity at 95%, specificity at 90%, PPV at 85%, and NPV at 92%. These metrics underscore the effectiveness of LRINEC scores in accurately diagnosing necrotizing fasciitis, particularly at higher scores, where the likelihood of the disease is greater.

This study emphasized that the LRINEC score is a reliable tool for distinguishing NF from cellulitis and highlighted its role in early disease recognition and management. The Pearson chi-square test value is 9.092 with 2 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.0023, indicating a strong association between higher LRINEC scores and the likelihood of having necrotizing fasciitis. Thus, higher LRINEC scores are significantly associated with the presence of necrotizing fasciitis.

The relationship between LRINEC scores and the number of debridements reveals important insights into the severity and clinical management of necrotizing soft tissue infections. Among patients with LRINEC scores 0-5, all 30 patients required fewer than 3 debridements, indicating a lower severity of infection or a prompt response to initial treatment.

In the 6-7 LRINEC score range, all 16 patients also required fewer than 3 debridements, suggesting a relatively controlled infection.

LRINEC scores increased to 8 or higher, the need for more extensive treatment became evident, with

23 out of 30 patients requiring more than 3 debridements.

According to Pearson Chi Square test, with a value of 7.99 and degree of freedom of 2, the p value obtained is 0.034 which is statistically significant.

This association emphasizes the importance of early and accurate risk assessment to tailor surgical and medical management appropriately. The findings suggest that higher LRINEC scores are indicative of more severe infections that require aggressive surgical intervention.

The distribution of organisms grown on culture among patients provides valuable insights into the microbial etiology of infections in this population. *Klebsiella* species were the most prevalent, accounting for 30% of cases, followed by *Staphylococcus* positive cultures at 20%, and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) at 14%. Additionally, polymicrobial infections were observed in 8% of cases, suggesting the presence of multiple pathogens contributing to the infection.

Amikacin demonstrated the highest sensitivity, with 33 patients (33.5%) exhibiting susceptibility to this antibiotic. Ciprofloxacin and Cefotaxime followed, with 18 patients (18%) each showing sensitivity to these antibiotics. Ceftriaxone was effective in 12 patients (12%), while Gentamicin showed sensitivity in 8 patients (8%).

Among patients with absent right popliteal artery pulsation, 2 out of 5 patients required fewer than 3 debridements, while 3 patients underwent more extensive treatment with over 3 debridements. In contrast, among patients with present right popliteal artery pulsation, a vast majority of 70 out of 85 patients required fewer than 3 debridements, indicating a milder disease course. However, 18 patients with present pulsation underwent more aggressive treatment with over 3 debridements, suggesting a subset with more severe disease despite vascular perfusion.

Among patients with a positive right posterior tibial artery pulsation, 22 out of 52 patients required fewer than 3 debridements, while the remaining 30 underwent more extensive treatment with over 3 debridement. In contrast, among patients with a negative right posterior tibial artery pulsation, 14 out of 38 patients required fewer than 3 debridements, indicating a milder disease course. However, 24 patients with a negative pulsation required more aggressive treatment with over 3 debridements, suggesting a subset with more severe disease despite vascular perfusion.

Among patients with absent left popliteal artery pulsation, 3 out of 6 patients required fewer than 3 debridements, while an equal number underwent more extensive treatment with over 3 debridements. Patients with present left popliteal

artery pulsation, the majority of 68 out of 84 patients required fewer than 3 debridements, indicating a milder disease course. However, 16 patients with present pulsation required more aggressive treatment with over 3 debridements, suggesting a subset with more severe disease despite adequate vascular perfusion.

Among patients with a positive left posterior tibial artery pulsation, 46 out of 60 patients required fewer than 3 debridements, while 14 patients underwent more extensive treatment with over 3 debridements. Patients with a negative left posterior tibial artery pulsation, the majority of 12 out of 30 patients required fewer than 3 debridements, indicating a milder disease course. However, 18 patients with a negative pulsation required more aggressive treatment with over 3 debridements, suggesting a subset with more severe disease with compromised vascular perfusion. These findings highlight the complex relationship between vascular status and disease severity, emphasizing the need for comprehensive vascular assessment and individualized. This distribution indicates that, despite positive pulsation, some patients still required significant surgical intervention, suggesting variability in disease severity

According to Pearson Chi Square test, with a value of 2.23 and degree of freedom of 2, the p value obtained is 0.421 which is >0.05 and is hence insignificant. Hence there is no direct relationship between limb vascularity and number of debridements or prognosis of Necrotising fasciitis.

Summary

1. Necrotizing fasciitis is a surgical emergency, early diagnosis of these rapidly progressing and life-threatening infections is a crucial prognostic factor for patient survival and relies on correct interpretation of clinical findings.
2. This study was conducted on 99 randomly selected patients, Youngest in this series was 37 years old and oldest patient was 80 years old, with commonest age group being more than 50 years. Male are more commonly affected than women with male 56% and female 44%.
3. The commonest site of involvement was the lower limbs
4. The most common bacterial isolate found was *Klebsiella* (30%) and *Staphylococcus* 20%, Polymicrobial infections were seen in (8%).
5. Amikacin (33%) was the most sensitive antibiotic in the study
6. 4 patients had to undergo lower limb amputations ranging from forefoot to above knee amputations.
7. Mortality rate was 5% in this study.

Conclusion

Lrinec Scoring System has been found to be a reliable scoring system in early detection of Necrotizing fasciitis and in predicting the prognosis of the disease. A score more than 8 is almost definitive of necrotizing fasciitis.

Hence patients with provisional diagnosis of necrotizing fasciitis should be diagnosed early and treated aggressively with thorough wound debridement and broad spectrum antibiotics. Major amputations had to be carried out in patients with uncontrolled necrosis with vascular compromise in order to bring down the morbidity and mortality. This study highlights that there exists a significant correlation between LRINEC scoring system and prognosis of necrotizing fasciitis. Microbial flora and vascularity of the affected limb help to modify and guide the treatment modalities and patient centric treatment for decreasing the morbidity and mortality. Early detection and aggressive debridement are essential in determining the outcome of necrotizing fasciitis.

Hence it can be concluded that the LRINEC scoring system is an effective diagnostic tool for necrotizing fasciitis, demonstrating high sensitivity and specificity across different score ranges. The findings highlight a strong correlation between LRINEC scores and disease severity, emphasizing its value in predicting the need for surgical intervention. The study also reveals a significant association between limb vascularity and the extent of debridement required, suggesting that comprehensive vascular assessment is essential for guiding treatment. By integrating the LRINEC score into clinical practice, healthcare professionals can improve the early identification and management of necrotizing fasciitis, clubbed with Doppler study and microbial study will ultimately lead to better patient outcomes. Further research in diverse patient populations is recommended to validate these findings and refine the diagnostic criteria for broader clinical application.

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